

Connection of dynamic and static data: A data lake for building digitalisation

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Abstract—The landscape of building data is expanding, with heterogeneous sources that are often treated as isolated silos across different building domains such as energy, architecture elements, or automation networks. This siloed approach creates a lock-in scenario, limiting the potential for effective data exploitation, including the provision of added-value services, artificial intelligence, or machine-learning activities. To overcome this challenge, ensuring data integration through interoperability mechanisms becomes crucial within building data management frameworks. In line with this perspective, this work introduces a data lake that harmonizes heterogeneous data sources from various building domains. The primary goal is to standardize datasets, ensuring the delivery of high-quality services to facilitate better decision-making. These datasets are enriched by interactions between static and dynamic datasets. This holistic approach aims to break down silos and unlock the full potential of building data for informed decision-making processes.

I. INTRODUCTION

The widespread adoption of advanced Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), Blockchain, or Big Data (BD), coupled with the extensive proliferation of Building Automation and Control Networks (BACN) in buildings, has led to a substantial increase in data generation within the building domain. This trend is instrumental in propelling the development of a Smart Buildings landscape, which has witnessed a recent surge in popularity of this concept.

The wide range of sensing data is a forecast that full-scale digitalisation will be achieved in non-residential buildings within the next decade. It is estimated that this transition will result in significant annual global cost savings in both the Engineering & Construction and the subsequent Operation

phases of buildings. Consequently, a significant growth in the overall volume of IoT-enabled devices for smart home and smart building management is expected, with projections indicating an increase from 233 million to over 980 million units by the year 2025 [1].

Despite the growing emphasis on digitizing building data over the last two decades and the continuous increase in data generated by the building stock, challenges persist in ensuring data quality [2]. Data plays a pivotal role in virtually every facet of the built environment – from how individuals and businesses engage with properties to the meticulous recording and analysis of a building’s energy consumption and construction details. These insights contribute to well-informed decisions regarding construction and real estate processes. Harnessing data-informed decision-making and digital enhancements can substantially improve operational efficiencies at minimal costs.

The lack of consensus on the meaning of data governance complicates matters [3]. These data sources operate in isolation, missing correlation between pillars [4], hindering their full exploitation potential. Addressing these challenges is essential for maximizing the benefits of the evolving Smart Buildings landscape.

To derive maximum benefits for the built environment and its associated stakeholders in this data-driven landscape, it is crucial to address various technical, social, and economic challenges. This process begins with dismantling the prevailing siloed thinking approach, followed by easing vendor lock-in constraints, and ultimately involves the standardization and homogenization of data acquisition and storage. This standardization is facilitated through the implementation of technical and semantic interoperability enablers [5]. Effective and holistic decision-making in the building domain requires the integration and enrichment of data from multiple sources, all

while taking into consideration the diverse needs and interests of stakeholders. By moving away from isolated data sources and embracing a collaborative approach, more informed and comprehensive decision-making processes can be achieved.

With such an objective, this work introduces a concept of an open and enriched data lake. This data lake is designed to amalgamate dynamic, static, and contextual data from diverse and heterogeneous sources. It aims to deliver more valuable information tailored to different building domains, leveraging Business Intelligence technologies. The federated conceptualization of this data lake involves the application of an automated and adaptable model, which is synced with dynamic time-series repositories. In essence, the data lake supports the entire data life-cycle management processes. From the ingestion and pre-processing of data to quality checks and normalization, it facilitates the exposure of multiple data views for analytics, services, or any other tools built upon it. This comprehensive approach ensures the effectiveness and reliability of the data lake across various stages of data handling.

This data lake has been developed in the context of the DigiBUILD project [6], which main objective is to modernize the construction sector by integrating advanced digital services able to enhance building management. The project's motivation is to replace traditional data silos with a unified, stakeholder-centric digital approach, using an open, cloud-based toolbox for creating interoperable buildings. Fed by the data lake, DigiBUILD employs AI analytics for energy management, develops digital twins for infrastructure planning, and aligns with the EU's decarbonization goals to achieve a climate-neutral building stock by 2050.

DigiBUILD project is demonstrated at multiple locations across Europe through nine pilots and ten real-life use cases, including residential, commercial, and office buildings. This approach intends to validate the effectiveness and applicability of the proposed technologies and frameworks.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Initially, in Section II, the data lake concept is explained. Section III gives an overview of the data collection methods, both static and dynamic, as well as the synchronisation mechanism for this repositories. Section IV includes an application example in the Heron case, which is a set of buildings located in Greece, where the synchronisation procedures have been tested. Finally, section V provides the conclusions and future work.

II. DATA LAKE CONCEPT

The generation of a vast amount of dynamic data originating from diverse sources poses a significant challenge in terms of organizing and linking timeseries data to the static data originating from the building structure and other external contextual data related to the building's district. To tackle these challenges, it is crucial to establish common data structures that bridge the static and contextual building data with the dynamic data from IoT sources. Towards this direction, the present work introduces these common data structures of a defined data repository referred to as a data lake. Fig. 1

illustrates the role of the data lake in the process [7]. It acts as a central hub for merging and connecting the various data streams.

Fig. 1. Data lake concept for the digitalisation process

The data lake has five main components as illustrated in the architecture diagram of Fig. 2 [7]. These include three Data Warehouse (DWH) components:

- A1 **Data Catalogue service** acts as the interface between the data lake and other upstream applications.
- A2 **Time-series database** stores the data streams of the buildings' IoT devices (sensors, meters, ...)
- A3 **Data Marts Storage** contains the data marts structures that are formed by combining dynamic and static data.

and two Knowledge Graph components:

- B1 **Graph DB** contains semantic graphs in the form of RDF (Resource Description Framework) TTL (Turtle) files (one per smart building or smart district project). These files link the dynamic data stored in the DWH with static data stored in Object storage using semantic web technologies.
- B2 **Object storage** stores static information in the form of open data files (BIM (Building Information Model) IFC (Industry Foundation Classes), CityGML, CSV (Comma Separated Values), ...).

Building upon this approach, the data lake is designed to provide a comprehensive, people-centric data framework for collecting and managing building data in a uniform manner. It ensures the implementation of minimal interoperability mechanisms at both syntactic levels (communication protocols) and semantic levels (common data representation). This holistic approach aims to streamline the handling of building data, promoting consistency and ease of integration across various systems and processes.

To establish the data lake, three distinct types of data from the building (refer to Fig. 1) are ingested:

1. Real-time building data, which encompasses dynamic information sourced from various sensors, smart meters, and other connected building equipment.
2. Static data. In this segment, it is compiled contextual data relevant to both energy and non-energy aspects

Fig. 2. Data lake components within the architecture

of the building. This includes details regarding the building’s geometry (such as IFC (Industry Foundation Classes) [8] or CityGML [9]), the placement of energy systems and associated sensors, user behavior during building operation, Digital Logbooks, energy performance certificates (EPCs), and Level(s) [10].

3. External data sources, such as weather forecast services, climate data, and market information. This systematic approach ensures a comprehensive and organized compilation of data for the data lake.

To enhance the coexistence of dynamic and static data within the data lake, ontologies and semantics are used as frameworks to enrich the data with metadata, facilitating the extraction of high-quality insights for energy services. The utilization of ontologies ensures data interoperability, fostering the creation of open, linked data that can be seamlessly shared through intelligent querying services. This, in turn, enhances the availability of data for robust big-data analysis.

III. DATA COLLECTION MECHANISMS: SYNCING DYNAMIC AND STATIC DATA

Data collection mechanisms rely on ETL (Extraction, Transformation and Loading) procedures, which are split into the dynamic and static repositories. Fig. 3 depicts the two ways to ingest data. On the one hand, the blue side indicates the dynamic (real-time) data that is collected via specific ETLs per pilot, according to the communication standards and protocols. On the other hand, static repositories provide mechanisms to enable the integration of BIM (Building Information Modelling) and/or other static data, such as CityGML models, EPCs...

In the way that the data lake is conceived, semantic graphs are the main data structures that bind all incoming data to the data lake in a format that can be easily queried by upstream application. To populate and store these semantic graphs in the data lake both dynamic and static data collection mechanisms should be established as analyzed next.

Fig. 3. ETLs for the dynamic and static data ingestion processes

A. Dynamic data

Within the data lake, dynamic data are collected and stored in the time-series database of the data warehouse (DWH) component as illustrated in Fig. 2. Dynamic data typically originate from the following data source types:

1. **Sensor devices** are devices usually installed inside building spaces to sense values of specific measures such as temperature, CO₂ concentration and others.
2. **Meters** are devices that measure specific quantities such as energy.
3. **Virtual devices** are imaginary devices that generate estimations of specific quantities that are outputs of simulation processes.

These data sources are heterogeneous by nature. Table I illustrates the diverse range of data sources for each one of the pilots (demo cases in the project) from which dynamic information is gathered. The primary datasets include building, occupancy, energy consumption, electric vehicle, photovoltaic, and comfort data. These datasets are obtained through various protocols, including MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport), FTP (File Transfer Protocol), open API (Application Programming Interface), or SQL (Structured Query Language) databases. Furthermore, the data is delivered in different formats, such as plain text, JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) and CSV (Comma Separated Values).

B. Static data

Static data describe the building fabric as well as the building’s district characteristics and other contextual information and can be extracted from the following two sources:

1. **Open digital files.** These files contain information in a digital form that can be easily extracted as it is in both human- and machine-readable format. These can be for example BIM files such as the ones conforming to the IFC standard, CityGML files defining the building’s district context, weather files describing weather contextual information and others.
2. **Documents.** Documents provide useful information and are particularly useful in case the open digital files are missing. These documents could be floor plans or other

TABLE I
PILOT INTERFACES TO GATHER DATASETS

Pilot	Interface details		
	Dataset	Protocol	Format
UCL	BMS	MQTT	Text
	EMS		
	Light Controls		
	Access Controls		
	Occupancy		
EDF	Ethera	Nemocloud API	JSON
	Ellona	Ellonasoft API	
	Wattsense	Wattsense API	
IASI	3PhaseMeters	InfluxDB	CSV
VEOLIA	BEMS	FTP	CSV
	DEMS		
EMOT	Charging Stations	API	JSON
	PV and building data		
	eV Data		
FOCCHI	PV	SolarEdge API	JSON
	Comfort, energy data	JotMotiqa API	
			MQTT
	Occupancy	Google Calendar API	CSV
Energy Consumption	Google Drive API		
HERON	Building Data	API	JSON
FVH	BEMS	FTP	CSV
IEECP	Building Data	MQTT	Text
		Netatmo API	JSON
NTUA	BMS	PostgreSQL	Text

printed documents which are provided by the buildings' stakeholders. To utilize the information contained in documents and convert it into a digital form manual work is required via the use of appropriate GUIs and ETL processes that populate respective data lake structures.

C. Synchronisation and connection mechanisms

At the core of data lake's structures, dynamic data are linked to static data using semantic graphs. These graphs are formed according to a DigiBUILD ontology that has been published online [11] and reuses concepts of REC (Real Estate Core) [12] and Brick [13] ontologies. The ontology consists of five modules, as illustrated in the top part of Figure 4. These modules comprise one core module (A1) and four additional modules (B1-B4), which categorize the DigiBUILD data types into four separate data domains:

A1. Core module. This module contains essential data types that establish connections between the data types found in the other four modules.

B1. Building module. This module includes the data types associated with the spatial information of DigiBUILD's pilots, their distribution systems, and the assets they encompass.

B2. Contextual module. This module contains building-related data types, including agents, vehicles, and external resources in the form of files or web services.

B3. Quantitative module. This module comprises quantity data types, or quantities, categorized into various groups: energy, operational, comfort, economic, performance, and environmental.

B4. Temporal module. This module includes metadata types for time-series data and their semantic relationships with data types from the quantity module.

The semantic links between dynamic and static data are established through the core module of this ontology. The structure of this module is expanded and presented as a UML (Unified Modelling Language) diagram at the bottom part of Figure 4. In this diagram, the classes borrowed from REC and Brick ontologies are displayed with green blocks, while the new ones are with blue blocks. According to this module, and as indicated in the diagram, every dynamic data source either real (sensor or meter) or virtual (virtual device) is represented by an instance of `brick:Point` class that is connected via the `brick:Timeseries_Reference` to a Timeseries entry in a respective data base.

IV. APPLICATION EXAMPLE: THE HERON CASE

HERON itself is a company group for production, supply, and trading of electricity with a clientele of over 260,000 and access to 1.5 GW installed renewable capacity. Thanks to the accessibility to clients, the pilot within the EU DigiBUILD project consists of a cluster of dwellings of multiple purposes that belong in the same building: 2 apartments, 1 commercial space and 1 electric vehicle (eV) charging spot for additional flexibility.

One of the main aims of this pilot is to integrate multiple sources of data, towards data interoperability by combining existing and under development processes in order to achieve carbon free buildings. To reach these objectives, within the pilot, activities are related to; (1) harmonisation of data collection processes from electricity smart meters, smart plugs, EV charging, RES assets; (2) application of self-supply services by matching EV flexibility and RES generation with electricity consumption 24/7; (3) assurance of interoperability between multiple data inputs; (4) development of smart home monitoring solutions and EV charging algorithms into new analytics and visualisations

A. Interfacing the HERON pilot datasets

The interface to gather data from the raw data sources is based on HTTP requests. A credential-based authentication system is used, where the pair user-password is embedded in the body of the HTTP request, whose result is a authentication token. Once authentication is achieved, the query for the devices (which comprise smart meters and smart plugs,

Fig. 4. DigiBUILD ontology and its core module

measuring three phases for power, energy, returned energy, and relay) is run. The latter process consists of formatting the timeseries data and the metadata, basically identifying devices.

Fig. 5 illustrates an extraction of the result of the time-series data. This data set contains the device id, which is mapped with the measurement (as stated before, one device could measure energy, power and relay status), the electricity phase, the value and the calendar id as the date in format "YYYYMMDDHHmmSS".

Fig. 6 lists a set of the metadata from the raw dataset. In this line, the devices information is compiled. The collected fields are: a) identifier; b) type of device; c) id of the device type; d) name; e) date when registered; f) measurements included in the device (multi-sensor). This information is key as it is the one mapped into the DigiBUILD ontology to keep synchronization between dynamic and static data. As depicted in Fig. 3, the dynamic sync flow sends these metadata to the static repositories to keep the knowledge graph (Section IV-B) up-to-date.

B. Knowledge graph generation

Heron's pilot data are structured in a semantic graph format employing Brick and Real Estate Core (REC) ontologies, depicted in Fig. 7. It is worth mentioning that the knowledge

sensor_id	f_value	calendar_id
domxm3-3494546EC9F0_relay_0	0.0	202405020820
domxm3-3494546EC9F0_power_2	60.0	202405020820
domxm3-3494546EC9F0_power_1	70.39	202405020820
domxm3-3494546EC9F0_power_0	110.55	202405020820
domxm3-244CAB436349_relay_0	0.0	202405020820
domxm3-244CAB436349_power_2	0.0	202405020820
domxm3-244CAB436349_power_1	0.0	202405020820
domxm3-244CAB436349_power_0	216.0	202405020820
domxm3-244CAB436229_relay_0	0.0	202405020820
domxm3-244CAB436229_power_2	0.0	202405020820

Fig. 5. Subset of dynamic data extracted from the HERON pilot ETL in form of timeseries

device_id	device_type	device_type_text
domxplug-C15499	4	Shelly Plug
domxplug-286D94	4	Shelly Plug
domxm3-485519C920CD	2	3-phase EM
domxm3-349454717657	2	3-phase EM
domxm3-349454718E54	2	3-phase EM
shellyplug-s-7C87CEBA3E4C	5	Shelly Plug S
domxplug-2C907E	4	Shelly Plug
domxplug-2CAB64	4	Shelly Plug
domxm3-244CAB436349	2	3-phase EM
device_name	home_id	registered_at
286-A/C	286	2023-11-10T09:38:08.801Z
286-WM	286	2023-11-10T09:37:36.982Z
287-meter-EV	286	2023-11-10T09:37:04.165Z
286-meter	286	2023-11-10T09:36:30.126Z
268-meter-EV	279	2023-10-09T07:43:49.362Z
279-TV	279	2023-10-09T07:42:35.404Z
279-A/C	279	2023-10-09T07:41:52.448Z
279-DW	279	2023-10-09T07:40:53.666Z
279-meter	279	2023-10-09T07:39:50.952Z
measurements		
["energy","energy","power","relay"]		
["energy","energy","power","relay"]		
["energy","returned_energy","current","energy","pf","power","returned_		
["energy","returned_energy","current","energy","pf","power","returned_		
["energy","current","energy","pf","power","returned_energy","total","tot		
["energy","energy","power","relay"]		
["energy","energy","power","relay"]		
["energy","energy","power","relay"]		
["energy","returned_energy","current","energy","pf","power","returned_		

Fig. 6. Example of the HERON metadata extraction from the ETL

graph is extracted from the metadata obtained in the previous step. That is, an initial step requires sharing data to build the graph. Further iterations update the structure, if necessary, for instance, when a new sensor is detected or a sensor is not functioning.

A solitary building node (highlighted in a red circle in Fig. 7) is instantiated 11 times (indicated by blue-numbered circles also visible in Fig. 7). Each instance of the building

